

Effect of Accommodating Strategy on Employee Satisfaction of Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

Igwe, M. O.* & Nnadi, C. S. O.

Abstract

The study evaluated the effect of accommodating strategy on employee satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to; examine the effect of response strategy on the staff relationship and evaluate the effect of scheduling on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The area of the study comprised of five (5) selected food and beverage Firms in Enugu metropolis and Member Companies of Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN) South-East Geo-Political Zone. The choice of these firms was due to high number of staff, Capital base above 10 million naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1002 selected staff of the study organisations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and seventy-eight (278) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and sixty-five (265) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analysed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analysed using Z – test statistic tool. The findings indicated that Response strategy had significant positive relationship on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 256), 6.312 < 8.155, P. < 0.05$ and Scheduling had significant positive relationship on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 256), 5.037 < 7.126, P. < 0.05$. The study concluded that Response strategy and Scheduling had significant positive relationship on the staff relationship and team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study recommended among others that to minimize or eliminate the potential impact the risk may pose to the achievement of set objectives; the management should use response strategy to actualize their goal and reduce treat.

Keywords: Accommodating Strategy; Employee Satisfaction; Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

*Correspondence: obiara***@yahoo.com (available on click)
Institute of Peace, Conflict and Development Studies
Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Nigeria

© The Author(s) 2024. This article is open access and is governed by a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. You are free to use, share, adapt, distribute, or reproduce it in any medium or format, provided you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source. A link to the Creative Commons license should be provided, and any changes made should be indicated. The article's Creative Commons license covers the images and other third-party materials, unless specified otherwise in a credit line. If your intended use goes beyond the permitted scope or is restricted by statutory regulations not covered by the license, you must seek permission directly from the copyright holder. For a detailed copy of the license, please visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. The Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication waiver (<http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>) is applicable to the data presented in this article, unless stated otherwise in a credit line to the data.

Introduction

Learning to let go of issues that are not important, put the needs of others who care about the issue first, and let you see things from other people's perspectives becomes the challenging areas in some organisations. The Accommodating style may lead people to take advantage of you if they know you can easily give up argument. Accommodating strategy is a selfless style of management which puts the needs and wants of the other party over one's own. This style does have some limitations and drawbacks. It is a style of conflict resolution which focuses on the needs and wants of the other party over one's own. It is a selfless style of management where the manager puts the needs of the other party before their own needs and wants. The manager will be flexible, compromising and understanding and will work with the other party to find a mutually beneficial solution to the organization. This is style of conflict management often use when the other party is more knowledgeable or experienced than the manager (Ma, 2023). Accommodating strategy describes when a person is cooperative, but not self-confident; in other to satisfy the other person's concerns at the expense of their own (Andy, 2023). Accommodating is viewed as the peace lover mode as it focuses more on preserving relationships than on achieving a personal goal or result. However, in a dispute, this creates a lose/win relationship where the accommodating party may make a choice to comply to the needs of the other, sometimes out of kindness and sometimes to avoid conflict or stress (Dale,2016).

Satisfied employees are also more likely to be creative and innovative and come up with breakthroughs that allow a company to grow and change positively with time and changing market conditions. Employee satisfactions is becoming more challenging for companies including those in the telecommunication industry due to a number of factors such as availability of the right talent in some fields, manager-employee relations, competition, differences in the level of employer-employee expectations, the high cost associated with hiring new talents, among others (Alasin, 2022). Employee satisfaction is frequently used to describe how your employees feel at work whether they are unhappy or fulfilling their professional wants and needs. Employee satisfaction is generally a positive concept and can significantly help your business. However, if average employees stay because they are happy and satisfied with your work environment, that can become a problem.

Many factors contribute to whether an employee is confident at work. This can include being treated with respect, receiving recognition for work, getting quality benefits and above-average compensation, and a positive management team. Employee satisfaction varies from one individual to the next. What may make one person enjoy their work environment could make another dislike it. One crucial factor to remember regarding employee satisfaction is that if your employees are satisfied but are not doing their jobs to the best of their ability, everything an employer does to provide a workplace environment that promotes satisfaction would be for nothing (Eric, 2023).

Statement of the Problem

The goal of accommodation is to help employees remain productive and feel supported in their workplace. Developing sustainable solutions is more likely to happen by engaging employees to help determine what will work for them. Any scenario in which employee live, work, and collaborate with others is susceptible to conflict. Because workplaces are made up of employees with different backgrounds, personalities, opinions, and daily lives is bound to occur. Employee cultural values impact their level of satisfaction and organizational commitment. Before implementing an accommodation plan, it helps to ensure the employee is engaged in the discussion to explore solutions that will effectively support their success at work.

Accommodating which involves yielding and making concessions to maintain harmony and foster cooperation. The problem facing he study include; poor response strategy; and scheduling. This involved party typically means giving them whatever they want. Accommodating each party makes them both happy, but can create problems with other employees later on. Accommodators set aside their own needs because they want to please others in order to keep the peace. Smoothing or harmonizing can result in a false solution to a problem and can result in feelings ranging from anger to pleasure.

Conflict in the workplace can arise from many sources, from idea grounded differences of opinion regarding business strategy to simple clashes between strong personalities. The important of business decisions are often made as a result of competing ideas, and disagreement can help expose potential problems before it is too late.

Accommodating is a valuable tool when preserving relationships and harmony is the top priority. Using the strategy of accommodating to resolve conflict essentially involves taking steps to satisfy the other party's concerns or demands at the expense of your own needs or desires. Therefore, the study examined the effect of accommodating strategy on employee satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the Effect of accommodating strategy on employee satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Examine the effect of response strategy on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State
- ii. Evaluate the effect of scheduling on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Research Questions

The following questions guided the study;

- i. What is the effect of response strategy on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the effect of scheduling on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State?

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study;

- i. Response strategy has positive relationship on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State
- ii. Scheduling has positive relationship on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Significance of the Study

The study was significance because it influenced by many factors, like the nature of the work itself, pays and benefits, workplace relationships and career development opportunities. While it's tricky to quantify, companies still try to keep a pulse on how their employees feel about their jobs.

The study is very important because companies with high employee satisfaction have lower turnover rates, improved efficiency and output, increased profit, and

sustained business growth. However, unhappy teams lead to higher attrition rates, increased onboarding and hiring costs, and a noticeable dip in productivity. The study is beneficial because when employees are satisfied with their job and workplace, they are more likely to stay committed to the company and its goals.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Accommodating Strategy

Accommodation is a fundamental aspect of hospitality, travel, and interpersonal relationships, reflecting a willingness to be flexible and considerate. Accommodating is rendering a place of temporary lodge for employees of the organization. An accommodating strategy involves neglecting one's own concerns in order to satisfy the concerns of others (Brown, 2017). The employee accommodation policy outlines the organization's commitment to providing reasonable accommodations for employees, ensuring equal access to employment opportunities and a supportive work environment. The employee accommodation policy template can help HR professionals create a comprehensive and compliant accommodation policy for their organization. The issue of workplace accommodation is vital to employees with and without disabilities, as well as employers and organizations (Man, Zhu and Sun, 2020).

Strategy is important because the resources available to achieve goals are usually limited. Strategy generally involves setting goals and priorities, determining actions to achieve the goals, and mobilizing resources to execute the actions (Freedman, 2016 & Igwe-Ukworji, Orga, and Mbah, 2023). Strategy is an action that managers take to attain one or more of the organization's goals. Strategy can also be defined as a general direction set for the company and its various components to achieve a desired state in the future. Strategy results from the detailed strategic planning process. Strategy deals with long term developments rather than routine operations, i.e., it deals with probability of innovations or new products, new methods of productions, or new markets to be developed in future (MSG, 2024). A strategy is all about integrating organizational activities and utilizing and allocating the scarce resources within the organizational environment so as to meet the present objectives.

The accommodation process is a two-way street: both employers and employees have obligations to fulfil in this process. Employees must participate in the accommodation process by providing sufficient information, so their employer can make an informed decision about appropriate accommodations and how they can be meaningfully implemented. Similarly, employers are obligated to genuinely consider any request for accommodation and to take active steps to make inquiries where the employer knows or ought to know of a need for accommodation (Zaman, 2022). The objective of the duty to accommodate is to ensure the employer is engaged in a serious effort to consider and assess the issue of accommodation in all of the circumstances of the case. Any accommodation policy should be applied to the individual circumstances of the employee such that their individual needs can be considered (Zaman, 2022).

Individuals adopting an accommodating style of conflict management have a high want for recognition and support from others. The accommodating individual is more apt to take a middle of the road attitude when an inescapable conflict emerges. These individuals tend to use apology or humour, or express their desires in an indirect way rather than coming straight to the problem. Kraybill (2015) refers to accommodating as a harmonizing conflict response. He stated that the harmonizing style has a low focus on the agenda and a high focus on the relationship. Individuals will often use this style when they want to fit in with the other party. When this style is overused, the individual will eventually become depressed due to the fact of always giving the other party what they want and always losing what is important to the individual. Accommodation is a means of carrying everybody along in the activities of the organization (Tamunomiebi and Azuka, 2019).

Components of Accommodating Strategy used in the Study include Employee Satisfaction; and Scheduling Response Strategy

Response strategy is an action plan on what individual will do. The main risk response strategies for threats are mitigate, avoid, transfer, actively accept, passively accept, and escalate a risk (Dmytro, 2023). A response strategy is a plan of action taken to address a particular risk. The purpose of a risk response plan is to mitigate a negative risk, also known as a threat, to an individual or company. What constitutes a threat

may vary depending on the business or individual, but typically, a threat is defined as something that has the potential to cause harm. Examples of threats that may warrant a risk response strategy include natural disasters, financial instability, data breaches, and product recalls. In some cases, a risk response strategy can also look to take advantage of a positive risk, also known as an opportunity. An opportunity is a potential situation or event that could have a positive effect on an individual or company (Nathan and Olga, 2023). Regardless of complexity, execution, or outcome, risk response is an inherent concern for most projects. Project managers typically design risk response strategies according to the specific needs of their projects. Understanding the workflow of risk response strategy creation can help you find effective, cost-efficient, and well-planned solutions (Indeed Career Guide, 2023).

Scheduling

Scheduling is the process of arranging, controlling and optimizing work and workloads in a production process. Companies use backward and forward scheduling to allocate plant and machinery resources, plan human resources, plan production processes and purchase materials (Marcus and Nilay, 2023). Scheduling is the process of planning, coordinating, and controlling the sequence of events and activities within a production process. Scheduling aims to ensure that resources are used optimally and effectively to meet customer demands. Scheduling is the process of planning, coordinating, and controlling the use of resources to complete a production process. Scheduling in operations management is often done using computer software that considers various constraints such as available resources, customer demand, and production capacity (Edureka, 2022). Production scheduling tools greatly outperform older manual scheduling methods. These provide the production scheduler with powerful graphical interfaces which can be used to visually optimize real-time workloads in various stages of production, and pattern recognition allows the software to automatically create scheduling opportunities which might not be apparent without this view into the data. For example, an airline might wish to minimize the number of airport gates required for its aircraft, in order to reduce costs, and scheduling software can allow the planners to see how this can be done, by analysing time tables, aircraft usage, or the flow of passengers (Marcus *et al.*, 2023).

Employee Satisfaction

Employee refers to the explicit delineation of an individual's professional status within an organization. The employee definition encompasses various facets, including contractual obligations, job responsibilities, and the overall relationship between the employer and the individual. The function of employee refers to the specific roles and responsibilities an individual is expected to perform within an organization, as outlined in their job description and employment contract (Tehsin, 2023). An employee is an individual who is paid for work completed by the standards of the company or employer (Rogers and Lord, 2023). Satisfaction can be defined as a post-purchase evaluation of a product or service based on pre-purchase expectations (Chiradeep, 2021). Satisfaction is defined as the level of contentment employees feel with their job. This goes beyond their daily duties to cover satisfaction with team members/managers, satisfaction with organizational policies, and the impact of their job on employees' personal lives (Chiradeep, 2021). Satisfaction is the act of fulfilling a need, desire, or appetite, or the feeling gained from such fulfilment (Vocabulary.com 2024).

Employee satisfaction refers to how happy and fulfilled people are at work. In HR terms, it's about how content employees feel with their jobs, the company, and overall work experience. When employees experience job satisfaction, their responses are multifaceted, positively impacting personal well-being and professional performance (Eric, 2023; Mbah, Nwatu & Okwor, 2021). Contentment in the workplace leads to heightened engagement, with employees willingly going the extra mile. Satisfied individuals often contribute to a more positive company culture, fostering collaboration and camaraderie among team members. Moreover, it catalyses employee retention, reducing voluntary turnover rates (Eric, 2023). Employee satisfaction is a measure of workers' contentment with their job, whether they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision (Thompson and Phua, 2017). Companies with high employee satisfaction have lower turnover rates, improved efficiency and output, increased profit, and sustained business growth. However, unhappy teams lead to higher attrition rates, increased onboarding and hiring costs and a noticeable dip in productivity. job satisfaction means the job meets your employee's needs and expectations. Many businesses also use it

to measure how happy and committed employees are to their work (Kinjal, 2023). When employees feel fulfilled at work, it shows in how they perform. They are more likely to invest the extra effort resulting in increased productivity, efficiency, and better overall job performance. Workplace happiness is a personal and subjective experience. It varies from one employee to another based on unique preferences, values, and needs. This means there is no one, universal way to improve satisfaction levels. Although factors may vary for different employees, some remain consistent (Kinjal, 2023).

Components of Employee Satisfaction

Staff Relationship

Staff relationship refers to an organization's efforts to maintain positive relationships with employees. The goals of good employee relations include inspiring employee loyalty, increasing engagement, reducing turnover, and creating a positive company culture (Deloitte, 2022). Employee relations refers to the relationship between or among an employer and its employees. Depending on the context, the term has both practical and theoretical applications. Certain companies may have a dedicated team for maintaining and improving employee relations and this term may refer to this team. In other cases, the term may refer to theories, plans and policies designed to support employees and their interests. Regardless of the approach, employee relations are typically overseen by a company's human resources department. Staff relationship concerns the building of positive relationships and interactions among employers and employees, and at a broader level helps foster a sense of community within an organization. This could entail initiating transparent workplace communication or supporting the emotional, physical and psychological health of employees. Ultimately, the goal of employee relations is to create a positive relationship between employers and employees that leads to an increase in employee retention, happiness and productivity (Crail & Watts, 2023). Employee relations are about reinforcing the ties between the employer and employees and making the company a better place to work. Strong relationships within an organization contribute to a positive workplace climate (Neelie, 2023). In other words, employee relations cover the contractual, practical, as well as physical, and emotional dimensions of the employee-employer relationship. It's a crucial factor when it comes to

overall organizational performance because good employee relations management translates into increased employee wellbeing and productivity. Employee relations can refer to either an organization's program or policies or a team of people that nurture the employer-employee relationship (Neelie, 2023).

Staff relationship has a direct influence on employee satisfaction and engagement. Therefore, many companies today invest more resources to improve employee relations and keep their workplaces healthy. Staff relationship is a term used to describe relations between employers and employees. Today's organizations are striving to become more agile, faster, and transparent (Kristina, 2023). Although Staff relationship and policies are typically intended to be non-biased and neutral (particularly when it comes to addressing and resolving employee-versus-employee conflicts), staff and policies are both ultimately responsible for protecting the interests and well-being of the company as a whole. Employees should beware employee relations staff and policies are not generally intended to protect employee interests (Crail & Watts, 2023).

Team Involvement

A team is a group of individuals, all working together for a common purpose. The individuals comprising a team ideally should have common goals, common objectives and more or less think on the same lines. Individuals who are not compatible with each other can never form a team. They should have similar if not the same interests, thought processes, attitude, perception and likings (MSG, 2024). A team is defined as a group of people who perform interdependent tasks to work toward accomplishing a common mission or specific objective (Thompson, 2018). An organization with many teams requires careful alignment. As teams and individuals link with other teams, the principles of developing understanding and trust will apply, but the structure will get more complex. Understanding the many interrelationships that exist between organizational units and processes, and the impact of these relationships on quality, productivity, and cost, makes the value of teams apparent. Working together enables us to tackle big projects and audacious goals that just wouldn't be possible alone. Effective teamwork empowers us to reach our goals and have far more impact. Teamwork stretches far beyond making the best snow fort or carrying the heaviest objects. But not everyone sees the value and benefits that a group

of people working together can accomplish (Perry, 2022). Mrinmoy (2023), state that hiring the best talents is not enough. To mould them according to your organizational needs is crucial. Employees' skills, expertise, and experience add a lot of value to any organization. But to bring the best in them, it is critical to involve your employees and practice a culture of collaboration. When employees take part in crucial management meetings it is known as employee involvement. It is the process of keeping the employees aligned with the organization's values and work ethics. Involving the employees gives them more autonomy for better performances. Achieving full potential will mean that your employees will love to work for you. And that itself is great news, and involvement will make them more loyal towards the organization (Mrinmoy, 2023). Employee involvement has contributed both impacts either positively or negatively on firm achievement. It also brings about misunderstanding to workers in their day-to-day activities due to unclear policies induced by the top management without any consultation made to them. Ineffective participation in decision making on efficiency of the organization can cause conflicts within an organization (Eneh, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

Two-factor theory (Frederick Herzberg 1968)

This theory was proposed by Frederick Herzberg 1968. The two-factor theory states that there are certain factors in the workplace that cause job satisfaction while a separate set of factors cause dissatisfaction, all of which act independently of each other (Herzberg, Mausner, and Snyderman, 1959). The theory posits that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are not opposites. Rather, certain factors must be present to avoid dissatisfaction. Other factors must be present to provide satisfaction (Gordon, 2023).

The study was founded on Two-factor theory by Frederick Herzberg 1968 because it was based on the assumption that there are two sets of factors that influence motivation in the workplace by either enhancing employee satisfaction or hindering it. Herzberg's research found that motivators were far more effective in motivating employee productivity. The theory provided a way to motivate through improved work conditions which lead to a burgeoning of job enrichment programs. The primary criticisms of this theory concern the definition of job satisfaction.

Also, there are issues in the ability to differentiate hygiene from motivators. In some instances, variations of a factor could be each. Hygiene Theory fails to address the quality of the relationship between management and subordinates (Gordon, 2022).

Empirical Review

The effect of response strategy on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Ede & Mbah (2020) conducted a study on evaluation of the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction among employees of five selected manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The objectives were to examine the relationship between promotion and employees' commitment to work; and regular payment of salary and employee productivity in five selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. The population was five thousand, and eleven employees (5,011). The sample size was eight hundred and ninety-five (895) was used. The finding shows that there is a positive relationship between promotion and employee commitment in the five selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. The study concluded that there is a positive relationship between promotion and employee commitment, regular payment of salary and employee productivity in selected bakeries in South-East, Nigeria. The study recommended that the salary and remuneration packages of the industry should be competitive with other sectors which make them recruit and source qualified and skilled employees.

Mbah, et al. (2020) conducted a study on how does product differentiation strategy influence output: an assessment of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. The study sought to examine whether product differentiation strategy influence output with food, beverage and tobacco firms within the South East of Nigeria. The study adopted Sprint Likert Scale. Data were analysed using F-statistics (ANOVA) tool. The finding showed that product differentiation strategy has positive effect on the number of purchases of manufacturing firms; the quantity of products produced and the improved level of production of the firms. The study recommended that organization should underline their products' unique attributes, features and value propositions to differentiate themselves from other competitors for the convenience of their customers.

Asenge, et al. (2023) conducted a study on the effect of turnaround strategies on firm performance in Nigerian foods and beverages manufacturing industry: A study of BUA Foods Plc. The study sought to examines the effect of retrenchment strategy and diversification strategy on the performance of BUA Foods Plc. The study adopted a survey research design. The population of the study was three hundred and forty six (346) was used. data were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 23). The finding showed that retrenchment strategy has a positive and significant effect on the performance of BUA Foods Plc. The study concluded that turnaround strategies help to reduce costs associated with business operations and improve performance. The study recommended that management of BUA Foods Plc should always launch new products or product lines into new markets to meet increasing customer demands and expectations so as to improve its performance.

The effect of scheduling on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Eneh (2022) conducted a study on the effect of employees' involvement in management decision making on organizational efficiency of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The objectives of the study were to ascertain the effect of employee feedback on organizational efficiency of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State and determine the effect of employee commitment on organizational efficiency of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study used the survey approach. The population of two thousand nine hundred and eighty-nine (2989), and sample size of four hundred (400) was used. The findings showed that employee feedback had positive significant effect on organizational efficiency of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study concluded that employee feedback and commitment are managerial practices whose effects widely impact the organizational efficiency. The study recommended among others that firms should communicate clearly the goals, vision, and mission clearly to the employees.

Mbah, Ekechukwu & Chukwudi (2022) conducted a study on the effectiveness of staff motivation strategies in manufacturing companies in Enugu State. The study sought to ascertain the effect of quality training on the employee commitment and the effect of recognition and reward of outstanding

performance on the output of employees in manufacturing companies in Enugu state. The population of four thousand three hundred and twenty-one (4321); and sample size of three hundred and forty-nine (349) was used. Data were analysed using the Pearson correlation coefficient (f-statistics (ANOVA) tool). The findings showed that Quality training has a positive significance on the employee commitment; recognition and reward of outstanding performance has positive significance on the output of employees in manufacturing companies in Enugu state. The study concluded that training as a motivation is an effective tool to enhance efficiency, productivity and workers retention in organizations. It increases that morale of the workers and commitment. The study recommended that training should be part of organizational activities to enable the workers acquire more skills and knowledge to work for the companies and retention assured.

Okolocha & Onwuchekwa (2023) conducted a study on work deviant behaviour and team cooperation in selected manufacturing companies in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study sought to ascertain the effect of workplace aggression and non-compliant to organization policy on team cooperation of manufacturing companies in Enugu, Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted. The finding shows that workplace aggression and non-compliant to organization policy have a significant effect on team cooperation of manufacturing companies in Enugu, Nigeria. The study recommended that corporate managers should focus on the effective management of attitudinal and behavioural outcome so as to foster conducive work environment and position the organization's image to the public.

Summary of the Review

Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to be more motivated and engaged. They have a sense of loyalty and dedication towards the organisation,

which often translates into increased productivity. Satisfied employees tend to provide better customer service, resulting in positive customer experiences, while unhappy or disengaged employees can lead to poor customer service and negative experiences. The study was anchored on Frederick Herzberg 1968. The theory holds that employee job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction are influenced by separate factors. The empirical review were based the objectives of the study (variable). Most of the previous studies were carried out in Nigeria and few were done outside Nigeria. None of the studies were seen done on the related topic of the present study "effect of accommodating strategy on employee satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State". Therefore, the study was motivated to bridge the gap in review.

Methodology

The area of the study comprised of five (5) selected food and beverage Firms in Enugu metropolis and Member Companies of Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN) South-East Geo-Political Zone. The choice of these firms was due to high number of staff, Capital base above 10 million naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1002 selected staff of the study organisations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and seventy eight (278) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and sixty five (265) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 86 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.77 which was also good. Data was presented and analysed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analysed using Z – test statistic tool.

The effect of response strategy on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 1: Responses on the effect of response strategy on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Clear mission statement maximizes staff effectiveness and them of communication.	580	332	66	52	18	1048	3.95	1.236	Agree
		116	83	22	26	18	265			
		43.8	31.3	8.3	9.8	6.8	100%			
2	The documentation of staff roles and responsibilities enhanced staff effort into cultivating the right work environment.	440	392	66	68	23	989	3.73	1.282	Agree
		88	98	22	34	23	265			
		33.2	37.0	8.3	12.8	8.7	100%			
3	There is cyber security awareness staff training which creates a more engaged situation.	475	400	66	40	28	1009	3.81	1.290	Agree
		95	100	22	20	28	265			
		35.8	37.7	8.3	7.5	10.6	100%			
4	The management has a proven process to identify potential incidents that promotes job satisfaction.	495	368	66	42	38	1009	3.75	1.380	Agree
		99	92	22	14	38	265			
		37.4	34.7	8.3	5.3	14.3	100%			
5	Higher level focus needs was on re-establishing business productivity with increased staff motivation.	455	312	108	58	31	964	3.64	1.359	Agree
		91	78	36	29	31	265			
		34.3	29.4	13.6	10.9	11.7	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.776	1.3094	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1, 199 respondents out of 265 representing 75.1 percent agreed that Clear mission statement maximizes staff effectiveness and them of communication with mean score 3.95 and standard deviation of 1.236. The documentation of staff roles and responsibilities enhanced staff effort into cultivating the right work environment 186 respondents representing 70.2 percent agreed with mean score of 3.73 and standard deviation of 1.282. There is cyber security awareness staff training which creates a more engaged situation 195 respondents

representing 73.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.81 and standard deviation of 1.290. The management has a proven process to identify potential incidents that promotes job satisfaction 191 respondents representing 72.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.75 and 1.380. Higher level focus needs was on re-establishing business productivity with increased staff motivation. 169 respondents representing 63.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.64 and standard deviation 1.359.

The effect of scheduling on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 2: Responses on the effect of scheduling on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Scheduling ensure that resources are used optimally that facilitates staff careful alimnt.	540	188	141	36	45	950	3.58	1.490	Agree
		108	47	47	18	45	265			
		40.8	17.7	17.7	6.8	17.0	100%			
2	Effective meeting of customers needs are as a result of scheduling and staff working together.	580	184	153	32	36	985	3.72	1.422	Agree
		116	46	51	16	36	265			
		43.8	17.4	19.2	6.0	13.6	100%			

3	Controlling the use of resources enhances production completion due to staff collaboration.	410 82 30.9	180 45 17.0	225 75 28.3	39 13 4.9	50 50 18.9	904 265 100%	3.36	1.445	Agree
4	The planning of human resources add a value to the organization by getting the expertise.	415 83 31.3	768 82 30.9	297 38 14.3	60 30 11.3	32 32 12.1	1572 265 100%	3.58	1.352	Agree
5	Scheduling promotes purchases of materials and achieving full potential of work together	420 84 31.7	244 61 23.0	156 52 19.6	30 15 5.7	53 53 20.0	903 265 100%	3.41	1.482	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.53	1.4382	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2, 155 respondents out of 265 representing 58.5 percent agreed that Scheduling ensure that resources are used optimally that facilitates staff careful aliment with mean score 3.58 and standard deviation of 1.490. Effective meeting of customers needs are as a result of scheduling and staff working together 162 respondents representing 61.2 percent agreed with mean score of 3.72 and standard deviation of 1.422. Controlling the use of resources enhances production completion due to staff

collaboration 127 respondents representing 47.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.36 and standard deviation of 1.445. The planning of human resources add a value to the organization by getting the expertise 165 respondents representing 62.2 percent agreed with mean score of 3.58 and 1.352. Scheduling promotes purchases of materials and achieving full potential of work together 145 respondents representing 54.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.41 and standard deviation 1.482.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Response strategy has positive relationship on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 3: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Clear mission statement maximizes staff effectiveness and them of communication.	The documentation of staff roles and responsibilities enhanced staff effort into cultivating the right work environment.	There is cyber security awareness staff training which creates a more engaged situation.	The management has a proven process to identify potential incidents that promotes job satisfaction.	Higher level focus needs was on re-establishing business productivity with increased staff motivation.
N		265	265	265	265	265
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.501	.452	.486	.471	.388
	Positive	.068	.087	.106	.143	.117
	Negative	-.501	-.452	-.486	-.471	-.388
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		8.155	7.356	7.909	7.663	6.312
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $6.312 < 8.155$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that

Response strategy had significant positive relationship on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $6.312 < 8.155$ against the critical Z- value of 2.18 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Response strategy had significant positive relationship on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Hypothesis Two: Scheduling has positive relationship on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 4: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Scheduling ensure that resources are used optimally that facilitates staff careful aliment.	Effective meeting of customers needs are as a result of scheduling and staff working together.	Controlling the use of resources enhances production completion due to staff collaboration.	The planing of human resources add a value to the organization by getting the expertise.	Scheduling promotes purchases of materials and achieving full potential of work together
N		265	265	265	265	265
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.408	.438	.309	.373	.317
	Positive	.170	.136	.189	.121	.200
	Negative	-.408	-.438	-.309	-.373	-.317
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		6.634	7.126	5.037	6.066	5.160
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $5.037 < 7.126$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that scheduling had significant positive relationship on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $5.037 < 7.126$ against the critical Z- value of 2.18 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Scheduling had significant positive relationship on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

From the result of hypothesis one, the calculated Z-value ranges from $6.312 < 8.155$ against the critical Z-value of 0.000, which implies that response strategy had significant positive relationship on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result in literature review, Mbah et al. (2020) conducted a study on how does product differentiation strategy influence output: an assessment of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. The finding showed that product differentiation strategy has positive effect on the number of purchases of manufacturing firms; the quantity of products produced and the improved level of production of the firms. Asenge, Okadimeji, Enyi and Adudu (2023) conducted a study on the effect of turnaround strategies on firm performance in nigerian foods and beverages manufacturing industry: A study of BUA Foods Plc. The finding showed that retrenchment strategy has a positive and significant effect on the performance of BUA Foods Plc.

From the result of hypothesis two, the calculated Z-value ranges from $5.037 < 7.126$ against the critical Z-value of 0.000 which implies that scheduling had significant positive relationship on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result in literature review,

Eneh (2022) conducted a study on the effect of employees involvement in management decision making on organizational efficiency of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The findings showed that employee feedback had positive significant effect on organizational efficiency of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Mbah, Ekechukwu & Chukwudi (2022) conducted a study on the effectiveness of staff motivation strategies in manufacturing companies in Enugu State. The findings showed that Quality training has a positive significance on the employee commitment; recognition and reward of outstanding performance has positive significance on the output of employees in manufacturing companies in Enugu state.

Summary of Findings

- i. Response strategy had significant positive relationship on the staff relationship of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 256), 6.312 < 8.155, P. < 0.05$.
- ii. Scheduling had significant positive relationship on the team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 256), 5.037 < 7.126, P. < 0.05$.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Response strategy and Scheduling had significant positive relationship on the staff relationship and team involvement of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Accommodating strategy describes when a person is cooperative, but not self-confident; in other to satisfy the other person's concerns at the expense of their own. Satisfied employees are also more likely to be creative and innovative and come up with breakthroughs that allow a company to grow and change positively with time and changing market conditions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following recommendations were proffered:

1. To minimize or eliminate the potential impact the risk may pose to the achievement of set objectives, the management should use response strategy to actualize their goal and reduce treat.
2. Scheduling should be of management prerogative to help guarantee and maintain stock levels, keep warehouses organized, and can account for all outputs.

References

- Alasin, C. B. (2022). Conflict management strategies and employee job satisfaction: An empirical study of federal and state ministries in Rivers State. *International Journal of Research in Education and Sustainable Development*, 2(2), 1-18.
- Armstrong, M. (2019). *A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice* (10th Ed.). London: Kogan Page.
- Asenge, E. L., Okadimeji, A. T., Enyi, L. A., & Adudu, C. A. (2023). Effect of turnaround strategies on firm performance in the Nigerian foods

- and beverages manufacturing industry: A Study of BUA Foods Plc. *International Academy Journal of Management, Marketing and Entrepreneurial Studies*, 10(1), 120-127.
- Brown, J. S. (2017). Principles of intrapersonal conflict. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 1(2), 135-154.
- Chiradeep B. (2021). What is job satisfaction? Definition, factors, importance, statistics, and examples. Retrieved from <https://www.spiceworks.com/hr/engagement-retention/articles/what-is-job-satisfaction/>.
- Crail, C., & Watts, R. (2023). What is employee relations? Retrieved from <https://ww.employee-relations/>
- Deloitte (2022). Diving Deeper: Five workplace trends to watch for in 2021, retrieved from <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/insights/focus/human-capital-trends/2021/workforce-trends-2020.html>. Accessed June 8, 2022.
- Dmytro N. (2023). Risk response strategies. Retrieved from <https://itpmschool.com/risk-response-strategy/#>:
- Igwe-Ukwurji, S., Orga, C. C., & Mbah, P. C. (2023). Risk Management Strategy and Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing firms in Enugu State. *Journal of Business Research and Statistics*, 5(2), 30-50.
- Mbah, P. C., Nwatu E. C., & Okwor, E. O. (2021). Compensation and employee performance of Deposit Money Banks in South East, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research Management (IJRM)*, 11(3), 2249-5908.
- Ede, T. E., & Mbah, P. C. (2020). Evaluation of the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction among employees of five selected manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(8), 379-388.
- Edureka H. (2022). What is scheduling in operations management & production processes? Retrieved from <https://www.edureka.co/blog/scheduling-in-operations-management/>
- Eneh, E. O. (2022). Effect of employees' involvement in management decision-making on organizational efficiency of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. *European Journal of Marketing and Management Sciences*, 5(1), 1-13.
- Eric, C. (2023). What is employee satisfaction? Measure and improve. Retrieved from <https://buddypunch.com/blog/identifying-and-fostering-employee-satisfaction/>
- Freedman, L. (2016). *Strategy*. Oxford University Press. I
- Gordon, 2022). What is Hygiene Theory? Retrieved from <https://thebusinessprUS/management-leadership-organizational-behavior/herzburg-two-factor-theory-defined>
- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., & Snyderman, B. B. (1959). *The motivation to work* (2nd ed.). New York: John Wiley.
- Indeed Career Guide (2023). How to create a risk response strategy in 5 simple steps. Retrieved from <https://ca.indeed.com/career-development/how-to-create-risk-response-strategy>
- Kinjal, D. (2023). What is job satisfaction? Meaning, importance, and examples. Retrieved from <https://www.togetherplatform.com/blog/what-is-job-satisfaction-meaning-importance-and-examples>.
- Kraybill, R. (2015). *Style matters: The Kraybill conflict style inventory*. Harrisonburg, Virginia: Riverhouse Press.
- Kristina, M. (2023). What are employee relations and why they are important. Retrieved from <https://haiilo.com/blog/what-are-employee-relations-and-why-are-they-important/>

- Man, X., Zhu, X., & Sun, C. (2020). The positive effect of workplace accommodation on creative performance of employees with and without disabilities. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1-5.
- Marcus, V. M., & Nilay, S. (2023). Crude oil scheduling," foundations of computer-aided operations (FOCAPO) 2003, pp 323-325.
- Mbah, P. C., Ekechukwu, C., & Chukwudi, G. F. (2022). Effectiveness of staff motivation strategies in manufacturing companies in Enugu State. *International Journal of Business Economics and Management Research*, 9(6), 1-21.
- Mbah, P. C., Ekechukwu, C., Ede, T. E., Ugorji, O. S., & Egbudu, P. C. (2020). Does product differentiation strategy influence output: an assessment of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. *Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(9), 1-13.
- Mrinmoy, R. (2023). Employee involvement: Why it matters in every organization. Retrieved from <https://blog.vantagecircle.com/employee-involvement/>
- MSG (2024). *Strategy - Definition and Features*. Retrieved from <https://www.de.com/strategy-definition.htm>
- Nathan, M., & Olga, B. (2023). Risk response strategies | Definition, types & examples. Retrieved from Risk Response Strategies | Definition, Types & Examples
- Neelie V. (2023). Employee relations: Retrieved from <https://www.aihr.com/blog/employee-relations/>
- Okolocha, C. B., & Onwuchekwa, J. A. (2023). Work deviant behaviour and team cooperation in selected manufacturing companies in Enugu State, Nigeria. Published in *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 7(3), 569-577.
- Perry, E. (2022). What will make or break your next role? Find out why teamwork matters. Retrieved from <https://www.betterup.com/blog/what-is-teamwork>
- Rogers, K., & Lord, I. (2023). Employee overview, types & examples. Retrieved from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/what-is-an-employee-definition-types.html>.
- Rouse, M. (2017). What does scheduling mean? Retrieved from <https://itition/9654/scheduling>
- Sigei, C. E. (2018). Factors affecting employee satisfaction in the manufacturing sector in Kenya: A case study of Kronos East Africa Limited. A research project submitted to the school of management and leadership in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the degree of bachelor of management and leadership of the management university of Africa. Pp 77.
- Tamunomiebi, M. D., & Azuka, I. H. (2019). Accommodation strategy and employee resilience of oil and gas servicing companies In Port Harcourt, Nigeria
- Tehsin B. (2023). Understanding employee function in 2024: An essential guide. Retrieved from <https://blog.airmason.com/function-of-employee/>.
- Thompson, E. R., & Phua F. T. T. (2017). "A brief index of affective job satisfaction". *Group & Organization Management*, 37(3), 275–307.
- Thompson, L. (2018). *Making the team: A guide for managers* (3rd ed.). Pearson/Prentice Hall.
- Vocabulary.com (2024). Satisfaction. Retrieved from <https://www.vocublaary/satisfaction#:~:t>
- Woko, E. B., Ukoha, O., & Alagah, A. D. (2018). Organizational climate and job satisfaction in the local manufacturing sector in Port Harcourt. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 4(4), 1-19.
- Zaman, N. (2022). Accommodating needs, not preferences. Retrieved from <https://wmodating-needs-preferences-n>

APPENDIX

Accommodating strategy -paulinus 2024

R/Q1	The effect of response strategy on the staff relationship of manufacturing	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Clear mission statement maximizes staff effectiveness and them of communication.					
2.	The documentation of staff roles and responsibilities enhanced staff effort into cultivating the right work environment.					
3.	There is cyber security awareness staff training which creates a more engaged situation.					
4.	The management has a proven process to identify potential incidents that promotes job satisfaction.					
5.	Higher level focus needs was on re-establishing business productivity with increased staff motivation.					
R/Q2	The effect of scheduling on the team involvement of manufacturing firm					
6.	Scheduling ensure that resources are used optimally that facilitates staff careful aliment.					
7.	Effective meeting of customers needs are as a result of scheduling and staff working together.					
8.	Controlling the use of resources enhances production completion due to staff collaboration.					
9.	The planning of human resources add a value to the organization by getting the expertise.					
10.	Scheduling promotes purchases of materials and achieving full potential of work together					